

Synthesis and Characterisation of some New Diaroylmethane and Acrylophenone Nickel(II) Complexes

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The biological activities, analytical applications and formation constants of 2'-hydroxychalcones have been extensively reviewed¹. The chelating property of 2'-hydroxychalcones has been reported². Nickel(II) forms a large number of square-planar complexes^{3,4} stabilised by strong nickel-ligand covalent bonding. The present paper describes the synthesis of nickel(II) complexes with some new substituted diaroylmethane and acrylophenone complexes.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) corresponds to 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry for the complexes. These complexes have no magnetic moment indicating that all the electrons are paired. This explains the diamagnetic behaviour involving dsp^2 hybridisation with square-planer geometry of Ni^{II}-diaroylmethane and -acrylophenone complexes.

The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibited a strong bands around 21 270 and 28 550—28 570 cm^{-1} which are commonly assigned⁵ to the transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ ($b_{2g} \rightarrow b_{1g}$) and $A_{1g} \rightarrow B_{1g}$ ($a_{1g} \rightarrow b_{1g}$). This confirmed square-planer geometry of the Ni^{II}- β -diketone complexes.

The ir spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes showed absence of ν_{OH} band which was generally observed at 3 500 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands. The carbonyl bands at 1 690 and 1 665 cm^{-1} of the free

ligands, were lowered by 50—60 cm^{-1} in the complexes which confirmed the coordination of carbonyl oxygen. All the complexes exhibited a band around 400—430 cm^{-1} (Ni—O). In the ¹H nmr spectra of the Ni^{II}- β -diketone complexes a resonance signal due to aromatic CH_s appeared at δ 2.3. There is singlet at δ 2.6 due to Co-CH₂CO while singlet at δ 8.2 is due to =CH—. The aromatic protons were observed as multiplet at δ 6.8—7.5.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. M.ps. were taken by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-180 spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Shimadzu IR-437 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian-R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by Farady's method at room temperature using tris(ethylenediamine)nickel(II) thiosulphate as a standard. The substituted diaroylmethanes and acrylophenones were synthesised by known methods^{6,7}.

Aqueous solution of nickel chloride and ethanolic solution of ligands, i.e. substituted acrylophenones, were mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio and ammonium hydroxide was added till the pale yellow brown complexes were precipitated out (pH > 4). The yellow brown complexes were washed

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

For Sl. nos. 1-6

For Sl. nos. 7-20

Sl. no.	Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X ₄	Y ₄	Y ₅	Y ₆	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
										C	H	N	Cl	Ni
1.	[C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ Cl ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	Cl	—	—	—	165	60.44 (60.56)	3.63 (3.78)	—	11.05 (11.20)	9.05 (9.26)
2.	[C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	—	—	—	230	58.60 (58.63)	3.60 (3.66)	4.20 (4.27)	—	8.80 (9.00)
3.	[C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	H	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	—	—	—	237	58.45 (58.63)	3.60 (3.66)	4.20 (4.27)	—	8.85 (9.00)
4.	[C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₄ N ₄]Ni	NO ₂	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	—	—	—	185	51.50 (51.54)	2.85 (2.95)	7.40 (7.52)	—	7.75 (7.92)
5.	[C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	NO ₂	CH ₃	H	H	—	—	—	155	58.60 (58.80)	3.30 (3.37)	4.20 (4.28)	—	8.90 (9.04)
6.	[C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₀ N ₂ Cl ₂]Ni	NO ₂	CH ₃	H	Cl	—	—	—	135	53.00 (53.04)	3.00 (3.04)	3.75 (3.87)	9.65 (9.80)	8.05 (8.15)
7.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₀ O ₆ Cl ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	Cl	H	H	Cl	110	62.60 (62.70)	3.35 (3.41)	—	16.20 (16.35)	6.50 (6.70)
8.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₀ O ₁₄ N ₄ Cl ₂]Ni	NO ₂	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	198	55.60 (55.75)	2.80 (2.83)	5.60 (5.66)	7.10 (7.17)	5.90 (5.96)
9.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₂ Cl ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	H	Cl	220	61.30 (61.33)	3.30 (3.33)	3.00 (3.11)	7.70 (7.88)	6.45 (6.56)
10.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	H	H	205	66.25 (66.40)	3.80 (3.85)	3.30 (3.36)	—	7.00 (7.10)
11.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₂ O ₆ Cl ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	Cl	155	68.10 (68.14)	3.90 (3.95)	—	8.70 (8.77)	7.20 (7.28)
12.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₂ O ₁₂ N ₂]Ni	H	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	OH	190	63.90 (64.00)	3.58 (3.70)	3.15 (3.24)	—	6.75 (6.84)
13.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₂ O ₁₂ N ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	H	OCH ₃	175	64.50 (64.65)	3.85 (4.01)	3.10 (3.14)	—	6.50 (6.62)
14.	[C ₄₆ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	H	CH ₃	240	66.95 (67.05)	4.10 (4.19)	3.20 (3.26)	—	6.80 (6.87)
15.	[C ₅₀ H ₄₀ O ₁₄ N ₂]Ni	H	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	160	63.00 (63.10)	4.10 (4.20)	2.90 (2.94)	—	6.10 (6.20)
16.	[C ₅₀ H ₄₄ O ₆ N ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	N(CH ₃) ₂	105	72.50 (72.50)	5.30 (5.32)	3.30 (3.39)	—	7.10 (7.13)
17.	[C ₅₀ H ₃₈ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	H	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	CH=	151	67.60 (67.64)	4.20 (4.28)	3.10 (3.16)	—	6.60 (6.65)
18.	[C ₅₀ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₂]Ni	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	H	CH=	160	67.60 (67.64)	4.20 (4.28)	3.10 (3.16)	—	6.50 (6.62)
19.	[C ₅₀ H ₄₀ O ₁₂ N ₂]Ni	H	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	235	65.20 (65.29)	4.30 (4.35)	3.00 (3.05)	—	6.40 (6.42)
20.	[C ₅₀ H ₄₀ O ₁₀ N ₂ .Cl]Ni	NO ₂	CH ₃	H	Cl	H	H	N(CH ₃) ₂	160	62.55 (62.63)	4.15 (4.18)	2.85 (2.92)	7.30 (7.40)	6.10 (6.15)

with water and ethanol and dried under reduced pressure (Table 1).

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